

VIANNA: An Interactive Visual Analytics Framework for Exploratory Analysis of Neuropsychological Test Data

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Abstract

Background and Objective: Longitudinal cognitive testing is widely used in dementia research to monitor cognitive change and study progression from mild cognitive impairment (MCI) to dementia. However, exploratory analysis of longitudinal test batteries is often hindered by fragmented workflows that rely on spreadsheets, static plots, and ad hoc scripts, which limit reproducibility, iterative cohort refinement, trajectory inspection, and multivariate reasoning. This work presents VIANNA (VIsual ANalytics for Neuropsychological Assessments), an interactive visual analytics framework designed to support exploratory analysis of longitudinal cognitive test data.

Methods: Based on a task-oriented design process, our tool integrates (1) an interactive hierarchy editor for semantic attribute organization, dimensionality reduction, and transparent attribute derivation; (2) an overview workspace for data exploration, curation, and selection; and (3) coordinated analytical components supporting cohort comparison, longitudinal trajectory analysis, and correlation exploration.

Results: We demonstrate our tool using the multi-visit AI-Mind dataset, illustrating how interactive visual analytics can support structured data exploration, data curation, cohort-based comparisons, and hypothesis generation in complex longitudinal cognitive test datasets within a unified interactive environment.

Conclusions: VIANNA provides a domain-adapted visual analytics framework for exploratory analysis of longitudinal cognitive test data. By integrating semantic attribute management, overview-driven cohort definition, and coordinated downstream analytical views, it helps address the complexity of high-dimensional multi-visit neuropsychological test data in research settings.

Keywords: Visual analytics, Longitudinal analysis, Neuropsychology, High-dimensional data, Interactive exploratory analysis

1. Introduction

As populations age, dementia has emerged as one of the most pressing public health challenges worldwide [1, 2], with nearly 10 million new cases each year. Large-scale longitudinal initiatives, such as the European AI-Mind project, aim to improve the early identification of individuals at risk of dementia through artificial intelligence-based predictive models [3]. Although predictive modeling plays a central role in this context, researchers must also be able to contextualize model output to generate insights, explore meaningful cohorts, and interpret longitudinal cognitive trajectories.

Digital neuropsychological tests and related digital health tools are increasingly used in dementia and cognitive aging research, generating rich, high-dimensional longitudinal datasets [4, 5]. The structure and scale of these

datasets increasingly challenge conventional analytic workflows. In practice, researchers need to iteratively identify data artifacts (e.g., missing values, incalculable measures, or outliers), define and refine cohorts based on evolving hypotheses (e.g., demographic characteristics, biomarkers, or performance measures), inspect these cohorts' distributions, compare groups and quantify effects, and examine temporal trajectories. However, tools specifically designed to support structured exploration, navigation, and interpretation of longitudinal neuropsychological data remain limited [6, 7, 8]. Consequently, these tasks are typically carried out through ad hoc combinations of spreadsheets, statistical scripts, and static visualizations, fragmenting the analytical workflow and hindering hypothesis generation [5].

To address these methodological challenges, we present VIANNA (VIsual ANalytics for Neuropsychological As-

assessments), an interactive visual analytics framework designed to support the exploratory analysis of longitudinal cognitive test data in dementia research. VIANNA was developed through a user-centered design process in close collaboration with clinical investigators, involving iterative refinement based on real-world analytical workflows and data characteristics [9, 10].

The framework is specifically intended as a research-oriented tool for exploratory data analysis and hypothesis generation. While VIANNA enables inspection of data at the individual level and integrates statistical comparison methods, it is not designed as a clinical decision-support system. Rather, its purpose is to support researchers in structuring, interrogating, and understanding complex, high-dimensional longitudinal datasets prior to confirmatory analysis or clinical interpretation.

VIANNA is grounded in two central design principles. First, it operationalizes the inherent hierarchical structure of cognitive test data, where measures relate to tests, cognitive domains, and derived constructs. This enables flexible, expert-driven semantic organization and dimensionality management. Second, it adopts an overview-driven, coordinated multi-view analytical workflow that supports iterative cohort definition, data quality assessment, and multivariate exploration within a unified interactive environment. These principles are implemented through two primary components: (1) a Hierarchy Editor supporting semantic attribute organization and transparent attribute derivation, and (2) an Overview component enabling interactive data inspection, curation, and cohort definition. Selected subsets can then be propagated to specialized analytical components for group comparison, longitudinal trajectory analysis, and correlation exploration.

We demonstrate VIANNA using longitudinal data from the AI-Mind study [3], illustrating how the framework supports structured exploratory reasoning, identification of data artifacts, and hypothesis generation in complex cognitive datasets. Importantly, the goal of this work is methodological: to provide a transparent and integrated analytical workflow rather than to report novel clinical findings.

In this work, we make the following contributions:

- **Conceptual framework.** We formalize a task-oriented analytical framework for longitudinal neuropsychological data, capturing the core activities involved in data curation, cohort stratification, group comparison, temporal analysis, and correlation exploration in dementia research.
- **Hierarchy-based attribute management.** We introduce a hierarchy-based approach for semantic organization and derivation of neuropsychological tests attributes, enabling flexible and expert-guided dimensionality management and aggregation in heterogeneous multi-visit assessment data.
- **Interactive visual analytics system.** We present

VIANNA and demonstrate its applicability through a real-world use case based on large-scale longitudinal CANTAB data from the AI-Mind clinical study.

2. Methods

2.1. Related Work

Analysis of neuropsychological test data is commonly performed using spreadsheets, statistical software, or scripting environments. Spreadsheet tools and packages such as SPSS remain widely used because they support data inspection, descriptive statistics, and standard hypothesis testing. Programming environments such as R and Python provide greater flexibility for custom analyses and visualizations. However, these environments often involve steep learning curves, shifting the focus from analytical reasoning to technical implementation [11]. Moreover, they generally lack native support for coordinated views or task-specific interactions, making them less suited for exploratory workflows that involve dynamic group creation and iterative comparison.

Interactive visualization has addressed similar analytical challenges in other biomedical domains. Prior systems in genomics and bioinformatics have shown the value of coordinated multiple views, matrix-based exploration, and hierarchical organization for reducing cognitive load and supporting iterative reasoning [12, 13, 14, 15]. In neuroscience, however, most visualization tools have focused on imaging, connectomics, or structural brain data rather than cognitive assessment data [16, 17, 18, 19, 20]. As a result, systems specifically designed for longitudinal neuropsychological test data remain scarce. Existing approaches rarely support, within a unified environment, the combination of semantic attribute organization, dynamic cohort construction, distributional comparison, longitudinal analysis, and multivariate exploration. VIANNA addresses this gap through a coordinated multiple-view framework tailored to the structure and analytical needs of longitudinal neuropsychological data.

2.2. Data

The AI-Mind project enrolled 1,022 individuals aged 60 to 80 years with MCI continuum across five European clinical centers. Each participant completed a baseline visit (V1), followed by three follow-up visits (V2–V4) at eight-month intervals. At every visit, participants underwent CANTAB assessment (see Table 1), EEG recording and cognitive screening (MMSE/MoCA and CDR) to ensure longitudinal monitoring. A comprehensive neuropsychological battery and blood sampling were additionally performed at baseline (V1) and at the final visit (V4) [3].

In addition, blood samples were collected for analysis of genetic and protein biomarkers, including APOE ϵ 4 genotyping due to its strong association with increased risk of dementia [21, 22], and plasma levels of phosphorylated

CANTAB Task	Description
Motor Screening Task (MOT)	Assesses sensorimotor speed and visual coordination through a simple touch-response screen task.
Paired Associates Learning (PAL)	Assesses visual episodic memory and new learning through an object-place association task.
Pattern Recognition Memory (PRM)	Assesses visual pattern recognition memory in a 2-choice forced discrimination paradigm.
Rapid Visual Information Processing (RVP)	Assesses sustained attention through a rapidly changing sequence of digits and target-pattern detection.
Spatial Working Memory (SWM)	Assesses working memory and strategy through a spatial search task.
Delayed Matching to Sample (DMS)	Assesses delayed visual recognition memory through a non-verbal matching task.

Table 1: CANTAB tasks completed by each participant during each visit in the AI-Mind project data collection phase.

tau proteins (p-tau217 and p-tau181), due to their association with tau pathology in Alzheimer’s disease [23, 24]. Sociodemographic variables were also recorded.

The integrated dataset comprises cognitive scores, biomarker measurements, and sociodemographic data in a single tabular structure with over 130 attributes per record and approximately 4,000 entries. Each entry corresponds to one participant at a specific visit, forming a high-dimensional longitudinal dataset with repeated measures over time.

2.3. Analytical Tasks

The design of VIANNA was guided by a user-centered methodology [9], involving researchers from the AI-Mind project throughout all phases of development. Initial questionnaires were conducted to identify analytical needs, followed by iterative refinement through prototype testing and feedback sessions. This process resulted in the identification of a set of core tasks that characterize the analytical workflow in longitudinal neuropsychological research:

Task 1. Data exploration and navigation. Inspect distributions, ranges, extremes, and drill down from cohort patterns to participant/visit details to identify trends, outliers or anomalies across attributes and participants.

Task 2. Attribute transformation and derivation. Derive analysis-ready variables (e.g., standardization) using transparent and revisable definitions.

Task 3. Data quality assessment. Identify missing, inconsistent, or erroneous values and correct or exclude them to ensure data integrity.

Task 4. Cohort definition and refinement. Interactively define cohorts using multiple criteria (demographic/clinical/cognitive/biomarker) for their subsequent analysis.

Task 5. Comparative analysis of cohorts or individuals. Examine differences between groups or individuals using visual and statistical methods to assess magnitude, direction, and significance of effects.

Task 6. Longitudinal evaluation. Analyze group-level and intra-individual trajectories across visits to detect temporal patterns, deviations, or clinically relevant trends.

Task 7. Correlation analysis. Explore associations, redundancies, and multivariate relationships among attributes.

2.4. Visualization and Interaction Design

2.4.1. Architecture and Workflow

VIANNA was designed to support the interactive exploration of longitudinal neuropsychological datasets, characterized by repeated measurements, heterogeneous attribute types, and clinically significant participant-level variability. In practice, analysts must repeatedly switch between distinct analytical modes, including data exploration and curation, attribute derivation, cohort definition, and task-specific inference such as group comparison, longitudinal reasoning, and multivariate association. To effectively support these tasks, we avoid monolithic dashboards and single-view paradigms, as they offer limited visualization design space, which typically constrain the available visual encodings and analytical states, often oversimplifying complex data. Therefore, VIANNA adopts a Coordinated Multiple Views (CMV) architecture [25], distributing complexity across specialized task-driven views, while maintaining global coherence through interaction and coordination.

As shown in Figure 1, VIANNA’s workflow is organized around two central components. First, the Hierarchy Editor defines the analytical scope by enabling structured organization and derivation of attributes. Second, the Overview component serves as a central hub

Figure 1: Modular architecture of VIANNA based on a Coordinated Multiple View (CMV) design. From left to right: heterogeneous data sources; the Hierarchy Editor for semantic attribute organization and derivation; the Overview Component for data navigation, quality assessment, and cohort definition; and specialized analytical components for comparison, longitudinal analysis, and correlation exploration.

for participant-level inspection, data quality assessment, and cohort definition. Selections performed within the Overview—through interactive filtering, sorting, or brushing—are propagated to downstream analytical components. To support iterative and dynamic analysis, these views can be explicitly decoupled from the global selection state. When detached, a view preserves its current data subset selection while analysts can refine cohorts in the Overview component, enabling direct side-by-side comparison between alternative cohorts or analytical states. This mechanism supports both small-multiples reasoning (replicating consistent views across conditions) and heterogeneous juxtaposition of complementary representations (e.g., distributions, trajectories, and effect summaries). Overall, VIANNA’s architectural design supports complexity management by allowing researchers to define tailored subsets that can be examined in depth in subsequent analyses.

2.4.2. Attribute Derivation and Management

In neuropsychological practice, meaningful attribute groupings and aggregations are rarely universal. Instead, they depend on the specific test structure, the analytical question, and evolving hypotheses and may therefore differ across researchers and studies [26, 27].

To support this variability, VIANNA provides a Hierarchy Editor (see Figure 2), an interactive, node-link representation, that leverages the inherent structure of neuropsychological tests, where measurements can typically be categorized by cognitive aspect, test, or a combination of both. VIANNA’s hierarchy functions as an analytic lens: it externalizes semantic decisions about how attributes relate, while defining the attribute scope for downstream analytical components. The set of currently visible leaf nodes determines which attributes are exposed in the Overview component, allowing analysts to transition between detailed measures and higher-level summaries during exploration (Task 1).

Analysts can iteratively refine the hierarchy through direct manipulation, including filtering attributes, reorganizing groups, and introducing new attribute nodes as their analytical process evolves. Attribute derivation is integrated directly into this structure through two types of meta-nodes: *aggregation meta-nodes*, whose children explicitly represent the attributes being combined, and *attribute meta-nodes*, which reference source attributes without encoding them as children. This second option preserves readability while supporting combinations that do not naturally fit a strict parent-child layout.

All derived attributes are defined through explicit formulas in the meta-nodes, using predefined operations (e.g., arithmetic aggregation, string-based functions) or custom expressions, specified using a text-based interface. Because formulas explicitly record their source attributes and transformation logic, they remain transparent, inspectable, regardless of whether inputs are structurally represented as children. This makes attribute derivation reversible in the practical sense that analysts can iteratively review formulas, regroup attributes, and restructure the hierarchy as their analysis progresses, rather than committing to fixed preprocessing steps (Task 2).

Overall, this design addresses attribute complexity as both a dimensional and semantic challenge. By enabling user-driven grouping and attribute derivation while preserving explicit provenance, the Hierarchy Editor supports scalable navigation and transparent analytical workflows without imposing fixed ontologies or rigid processing pipelines.

2.4.3. Data Navigation and Cohort Definition

The task analysis presented in Section 2.3 indicates that early-stage reasoning requires a view that supports both global orientation and record-level traceability. In particular, Task 1 involves navigating between population-level patterns and individual observations; Task 3 requires making artifacts and missingness directly visible; and Task 4

Figure 2: Example of a hierarchy used in the VIANNA use case. Attributes are semantically organized by neuropsychological test (e.g., DMS, RVP, SWM, PAL, and PRM) and comprise both original and derived variables. Circular nodes represent original attributes, triangular nodes represent derived attributes without children, and square nodes represent derived attributes with children. Node color indicates attribute type: blue for numerical, orange for categorical, and gray for unknown. The set of visible leaf nodes determines the attributes available to downstream analytical components, and the hierarchy can be interactively expanded or collapsed to modify the analytical granularity. This structure facilitates semantic organization, control of dimensionality, and transparent representation of derived variables in longitudinal neuropsychological datasets.

benefits from reusing the same navigation and selection mechanisms to define and refine cohorts. Together, these requirements motivated the design of an Overview component as a central element of VIANNA’s architecture. Following Shneiderman’s mantra—“overview first, zoom and filter, then details on demand” [28]—this component should enable the inspection of the full dataset while progressively narrowing analytical focus.

We selected Navio [29] as the core view of this component, fulfilling the main requirements identified in the task and data analysis. Navio represents each observation as a row of cells and adapts color mappings to the semantics of each attribute type (e.g., sequential scales for strictly positive measures and diverging scales for signed values). Combined with column sorting and filtering, this representation facilitates the identification of distribution patterns, outliers, and attribute-specific trends that are difficult to detect using aggregate summaries alone (see Figure 3).

Navio also provides interactive selection mechanisms, including slice-and-dice filtering and brushing interactions over ordered attributes, allowing analysts to navigate and progressively define and refine subsets of records. Each selection generates a linked view, enabling side-by-side comparison of subsets and supporting iterative exploration workflows (Task 1). These interactions directly facilitate cohort definition through flexible combinations of demo-

graphic, clinical, and cognitive criteria, which can subsequently be propagated to analytical components (Task 4).

By integrating overview visualizations, interactive navigation, and cohort definition within a coordinated view, the Overview component serves as the central hub for early-stage analytical reasoning, enabling structured exploration while maintaining analytical control, transparency, and data integrity throughout the workflow.

2.4.4. Data Quality Assessment

In VIANNA, missing values and placeholder codes are explicitly encoded in the Overview and become especially salient under sorting and filtering, enabling rapid detection of data gaps, inconsistencies, and systematic missingness patterns (Task 3). We complement these encodings with lightweight, reversible edit operations to mark values as missing or apply basic imputations, ensuring consistent treatment of absent or incomplete data during subsequent downstream analyses.

To support transparent and iterative data curation, we introduce the Quarantine view, which maintains an independent inclusion/exclusion state. Analysts can move records into the Quarantine directly from the Overview to inspect, annotate, or correct them without permanently discarding potentially valuable information. Quarantined records remain accessible and can be restored at any time

Figure 3: VIANNA’s Overview component displaying participant-level data as a tabular visualization with cell-level color encodings adapted to the attribute type. Each column represents an attribute and each row corresponds to a participant-visit record. The leftmost panel shows the full dataset (3,552 records), while subsequent panels display filtered subsets based on progressively applied criteria. Active filters are shown below each panel, and subset sizes are indicated at the bottom. This coordinated layout enables direct comparison between cohorts while preserving record-level traceability and supporting iterative cohort refinement. The left panel shows the links to: (a) the management panel; (b) the hierarchy editor; (c) the analysis components, from top to bottom, Comparison, Evolution and Correlation components; (d) the Quarantine component; (e) interaction options with the overview component, from left to right, send selection to quarantine, switch selection with quarantine, display color legend, edit selection column values, download data, settings.

or even used as the active analysis dataset, enabling careful examination of edge cases and deliberate, well-documented inclusion decisions.

2.4.5. Specialized Analysis

For cohort comparison, the system combines distributional visualization with inferential statistics in the Comparison component. This design reflects current recommendations that statistical comparison should not rely on p-values alone [30, 31, 32]. Accordingly, the component reports whether the assumptions of normality and homoscedasticity are satisfied across selected cohorts, helping users choose an appropriate test. When a test is run, the interface presents group means with 95% confidence intervals, effect sizes, and a textual summary of the test statistic, p-value, and descriptive measures. In addition,

Test	N groups	Data type
Student t-test	= 2	Numerical
Welch’s t-test	= 2	Numerical
Mann–Whitney U	= 2	Non-normal/Ordinal
ANOVA One-way	≥ 2	Numerical
Welch ANOVA	≥ 2	Numerical
Kruskal–Wallis	≥ 2	Non-normal/Ordinal
Chi-Square	≥ 2	Categorical

Table 2: Statistical tests available in the Comparison component.

attributes can be ranked according to the magnitude of between-group differences, enabling users to prioritize the most discriminative variables. The available statistical tests are summarized in Table 2

Figure 4: Several views of the analytical components: (a) distribution of four cohorts shown as boxplots with overlaid individual observations; (b) forest plot summarizing pairwise effect sizes between cohorts; (c) ranking of omnibus effect sizes across attributes; (d) longitudinal evolution of two cohorts across visits; (e) PCA projection based on 29 variables, with an active lasso selection used to define PCA-based cohorts; and (f) scatterplot matrix showing correlations among attributes from the RVP test.

Test	N visits	Data type
Paired t-test	= 2	Numerical
Sign test	= 2	Non-normal/Ordinal
RM ANOVA	≥ 2	Numerical
Friedman test	≥ 3	Non-normal/Ordinal
Mauchly’s test	≥ 3	Numerical

Table 3: Statistical tests available in the Evolution component.

To support longitudinal reasoning, VIANNA provides the Evolution component, which enables interactive examination of numerical attributes across repeated assessment visits. Individual trajectories can be displayed together with group-level summaries, allowing analysts to assess both overall temporal trends and within-group heterogeneity. This dual view helps determine whether apparent group-level effects reflect consistent change across participants or are driven by specific subgroups. The component supports flexible comparison of multiple cohorts, selective highlighting of individuals, and visual augmentation of group summaries with standard deviation bands or 95% confidence intervals. To complement visual inspection, the component integrates multiple statistical tests, which are summarized in Table 3 and an implementation of linear mixed models (LMMs).

To examine associations between variables, VIANNA incorporates a Correlation component for structured multivariate exploration. Assessing relationships between attributes is central to identifying redundancy, latent structure, and potential associations in multivariate datasets [33], especially in neuropsychological research, where several measures may capture overlapping cognitive constructs or common underlying factors. Accordingly, the component integrates three views: a correlation matrix for compact inspection of pairwise linear relationships [34]; a scatterplot matrix for detailed analysis of selected variable pairs, including non-linear trends, heteroscedasticity, and outliers, together with coordinated brushing for cross-view subset analysis [35, 36, 37]; and two-dimensional PCA projections to summarize global structure, reveal how selected attribute subsets characterize the data, and support the direct cohort definition [38].

Together, these specialized components support statistically informed comparison, trajectory-based longitudinal interpretation, and multivariate pattern discovery, thereby addressing Task 5, Task 6, and Task 7.

3. Results

3.1. Implementation

VIANNA was implemented as a web-based application using React, D3.js, and Arquero.js [39, 40]. Within AI-Mind, it was deployed in the TSD [41] secure research environment and integrated into the project platform.

VIANNA can also operate as a standalone web application in publicly accessible hosting environments. An online demonstration instance is available¹, where users can access the application, source code, and demo videos.

3.2. Use case: AI-Mind Data

To illustrate VIANNA’s support for exploratory longitudinal neuropsychological analysis, we present a short walkthrough on the AI-Mind CANTAB dataset (see Appendix Appendix A). The goal is not to report novel clinical findings, but to demonstrate how VIANNA integrates attribute scoping, data quality handling, cohort definition, and coordinated downstream analyses within a single interactive workflow. Such analyses are deferred to future work, where VIANNA will be used primarily as a methodological tool.

Customize Hierarchy. We begin the analysis with the Hierarchy Editor, to handle the complexity of the dataset and define the attribute scope of the session. Using editor interactions such as node creation, brushing-based selection, and node reassignment, we build a new attribute hierarchy. At the top level, we grouped attributes by their CANTAB test and a specific node for sociodemographic data. This structure provides a clear separation between tests and sociodemographic variables, serving as a starting point for further refinement.

The editor supports transparent and interactive feature construction. Leveraging these capabilities, we replace clusters of closely related measures with representative variables or composites when appropriate to reduce redundancy. For example, the DMS test includes multiple attributes counting correct responses across different stimulus delays (e.g., 0s, 4s, 12s, all delays and simultaneous). We represent this set using a single summary measure, *DMSTC* (DMS Total Correct).

In addition, we normalized a subset of attributes—identified by domain experts as particularly relevant—by computing their *Z*-scores, to allow consistent comparisons among these measures. For instance, for the RVP test, attributes such as *RVPA*, *RVPMDL*, and *RVPPFA* are standardized (see Figure 2).

Initial Data Inspection. After establishing a semantically meaningful hierarchy that alleviates data complexity, we first scope the Overview component to sociodemographic variables to perform a rapid plausibility check. Using sorting and value-based selection we inspect marginal distributions and identify coarse longitudinal structure. For instance we sorted by the *Visit* column to see if we have the same number of visits across timestamps. This reveals 1,021 records for Visit 1, 942 for Visit 2, 870 for Visit 3, and 719 for Visit 4, consistent with longitudinal attrition. In addition, inspection of participants ordered by the *education* attribute suggests a possible imbalance in educational

¹<https://vianna.es>

levels across *site* cohorts. Selecting records from countries 1 and 4 at visit 4 illustrates these imbalances by showing clear differences in the content of the education column. (see Figure 3). Next, we focused our initial analysis on the RVP and DMS tests by collapsing the rest of test nodes.

Data Curation. To address missingness, we apply VIANNA’s automated clean-up operation, which transfers records containing missing values into the Quarantine while preserving their accessibility for inspection. This operation moves 329 records to Quarantine, leaving 3,223 records for subsequent analyses.

Inspection of quarantined records suggests two predominant patterns: (i) a subset with invalid RVP and DMS values despite evidence that the participant attended the visit (confirmed by re-expanding other tests and observing valid values elsewhere), consistent with misunderstanding or failure to complete the RVP/DMS task; and (ii) a subset corresponding to missed visits, indicated by missing values across all attributes for that visit. This example illustrates how VIANNA helps distinguish qualitatively different forms of missing or non-informative data and supports informed decisions about how each subset should be treated in downstream analyses.

Group Comparison and Hypothesis Testing. To illustrate confirmatory analysis grounded in exploratory observations, we revisit the education imbalance identified during Overview inspection. We first restrict the cohort to Visit 4 in the Overview component to focus on participants who completed the study. Then we invoked a distribution view for the education attribute and performed a Chi-Squared test to evaluate whether education distributions differ across countries. The resulting forest plot indicated small-to-moderate between-country differences, with effect sizes ranging from 0.2 to 0.5 Cramér’s V .

To illustrate exploration of statistically significant differences, we classified the available attributes using Welch’s ANOVA, leveraging its robustness to heteroscedasticity. The highest-ranked effects are dominated by DMS test measures. Selecting a bar drills down into a corresponding post-hoc test, enabling analysts to identify the pairs driving the omnibus effect, and in this case to verify that multiple differences reach medium-to-large magnitude across site pairs.

4. Discussion

The primary contribution of VIANNA lies in its support for the exploratory stage of data analysis through a task-oriented visual analytics workflow tailored to longitudinal cognitive test data. Rather than distributing key analytical activities—such as attribute management, data curation, cohort definition, and statistical comparison—across heterogeneous tools and disconnected processing steps, VIANNA integrates these operations into

a single, coordinated environment in which analytical decisions remain explicit, traceable, and iteratively revisable. This integration is particularly relevant in the context of high-dimensional longitudinal datasets, where analytical reasoning is inherently iterative and interdependent. Decisions regarding variable selection, cohort construction, and data inclusion are not independent steps but evolve dynamically and influence downstream interpretation. By preserving these dependencies within a unified workflow, VIANNA supports a more transparent and reproducible exploratory process compared to conventional fragmented pipelines.

A central methodological aspect of the framework is its treatment of attribute complexity as both a dimensional and semantic problem. In longitudinal cognitive datasets such as AI-Mind, heterogeneity arises not only from the number of variables but also from their hierarchical and conceptual relationships. Through the Hierarchy Editor, VIANNA enables users to explicitly define and manipulate these relationships, allowing semantic grouping, transformation, and derivation of variables in a transparent and reversible manner. This shifts feature engineering from a static preprocessing step to an integral part of the analytical workflow, guided by domain expertise. The Overview component complements this by providing a bridge between population-level patterns and record-level inspection, enabling users to identify outliers, assess data quality, and iteratively define cohorts. The integration of a Quarantine mechanism further supports transparent data curation by allowing temporary exclusion and inspection of problematic records without irreversible data loss. Together, these features contribute to a provenance-aware analytical process in which transformations and selection steps remain interpretable and auditable.

The specialized analytical components extend this workflow by supporting statistically informed comparison, longitudinal trajectory analysis, and multivariate exploration. Importantly, these components are designed to assist exploratory reasoning rather than to provide confirmatory evidence. Given the interactive and iterative nature of cohort definition and variable selection, statistical results—including p-values and effect sizes—should be interpreted with caution, particularly in the presence of multiple comparisons and user-driven subgroup analyses. Although VIANNA enables inspection of individual-level data and integrates statistical testing, it is important to emphasize that the framework is not intended for clinical decision-making. It has not been validated within regulatory frameworks such as the Medical Device Regulation (MDR) or equivalent standards, and its outputs should be interpreted strictly within a research context.

The AI-Mind use case illustrates the applicability of VIANNA to a real-world, large-scale longitudinal dataset. However, the current evaluation is based on an expert-driven qualitative analysis rather than a formal user study. While the system was developed through iterative collaboration with domain experts, future work should include

quantitative usability assessments and performance evaluations across a broader range of users and datasets.

Another limitation concerns generalizability. VIANNA was developed within the specific context of the AI-Mind study, which shaped both the structure of the data and the analytical tasks addressed. While the underlying architecture is broadly applicable to tabular longitudinal datasets, adaptation to other cognitive test batteries or multimodal clinical datasets may require additional effort. Future work will focus on evaluating the framework across diverse datasets and extending its capabilities to support more heterogeneous data modalities.

From a computational perspective, the current implementation relies primarily on client-side processing, which supports interactive analysis for datasets of the size considered in this study. Scaling to substantially larger cohorts or higher-dimensional datasets will likely require optimization strategies, including server-side processing or distributed architectures.

Overall, VIANNA contributes a domain-adapted visual analytics methodology for exploratory analysis of longitudinal cognitive test data. Its value lies not only in combining multiple analytical views, but in integrating data structuring, curation, cohort definition, and statistical exploration into a single, coherent, and transparent workflow. By doing so, the framework addresses a key gap between the increasing complexity of modern research datasets and the limitations of traditional analytical tool chains, supporting more efficient and interpretable exploratory data analysis.

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Declaration of competing interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Code availability

The source code of VIANNA is publicly available at <https://github.com/jorgeacostaupm/vianna>. An online demonstration instance is available at <https://vianna.es>.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

- Jorge Acosta-Hernández: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Visualization, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft.
- Pablo Toharia: Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

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Appendix A. Walkthrough in Images

Figure A.1: Expanded hierarchy view showing the full set of available attributes before meaningful grouping and abstraction. This image highlights the dimensional complexity of the raw dataset and motivates semantic structuring in the Hierarchy Editor.

Figure A.2: Refined hierarchy used in the walkthrough, with attributes grouped by neuropsychological test and selected derived variables incorporated into the structure. This organized view defines the attribute scope propagated to the Overview and downstream analytical components.

Figure A.3: The custom hierarchy limiting the scope to sociodemographic variables. This stage defines the first analytical scope used for initial inspection.

(a)

(b)

Figure A.4: Overview panel showing the cohort restricted to: a) Visit 1; b) Visit 3.

Figure A.5: Overview panel showing education imbalances across sites.

Figure A.6: Overview of the Sociodemographic, DMS and RVP attributes. The display supports early-stage plausibility checking, inspection of missingness patterns, and coarse identification of cohort structure before targeted filtering. Missing or invalid values are highlighted in yellow.

Figure A.7: The Quarantine component containing records moved out of the main analysis set due to missing or invalid values. This view supports transparent inspection of problematic cases before exclusion, correction, or reintegration into downstream analyses. Missing or invalid values are highlighted in yellow.

Figure A.8: Linked Overview scoped to Sociodemographic, DMS and RVP attributes, showing the cohort restricted to Visit 4.

Figure A.9: The Comparison component showing distributional views for the categorical variable education across site groups, together with pairwise effect sizes and a ranking of variables using Welch's ANOVA. This view illustrates how exploratory observations from the Overview can be followed by formal group comparison and post-hoc inspection.